

Post-agrogenic dynamics of molecular composition of humic acids in North-West Russia

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Today, a significant amount of land has transitioned from agricultural use to fallow state. These lands are undergoing processes such as shrub encroachment, waterlogging, and afforestation, which lead to degradation and the loss of carbon from soils. According to estimates by N. Ramankutty and J. Foley [1], up to $1.5 \cdot 10^6$ hectares of arable land have been lost from agricultural use. The majority of these lands are located in economically developed countries in Eastern Europe, Southeast Asia, as well as post-Soviet countries [2]. While it is known that this shift alters soil carbon stocks, the dynamics of the molecular composition of soil organic matter (SOM), which determines its long-term stability, remain poorly understood. The critical question is whether the natural restoration on fallow lands leads to the formation of stable, recalcitrant organic matter or to the accumulation of a labile carbon pool vulnerable to degradation, with major implications for carbon sequestration strategies and land management. Thus, this study aims to investigate the dynamics of the molecular composition of HAs extracted from post-agrogenic soils of the taiga zone of North-West Russia. To analyze the carbon state of soils on fallow lands in the North-West of Russia, a calculation of the content and stock of carbon in the soils was carried out, as well as elemental and molecular composition of humic acids (HAs) extracted from the soils was performed. To investigate the dynamics of molecular composition, the ^{13}C NMR spectroscopy method was used.

The analysis confirmed that soil carbon stocks decrease initially after abandonment but recover with time, approaching background levels as organic litter (Oi) horizons form. However, the molecular investigation revealed a counterintuitive trend: the elemental and structural composition of HAs showed a decrease in the content of stable aromatic carbon fragments and an increase in labile aliphatic fragments with increasing fallow age. HAs from fallow soils exhibited higher oxidation levels (higher O/C ratios) compared to those from native soils. The most mature and stable molecular structures were identified not in the oldest fallows, but in the mineral horizons of the background native ecosystems. The study concludes that while post-agrogenic succession leads to the accumulation of organic carbon, it primarily results in the formation of a labile carbon pool prone to biodegradation rather than a stable one. The molecular destabilization of HAs over time indicates that prolonged fallow state may not ensure long-term carbon sequestration and could even increase the ecosystem's vulnerability to carbon loss upon disturbance. These findings highlight the need for strategic management of fallow lands, suggesting that recultivation efforts should prioritize recently abandoned areas where the labile carbon pool is smaller, to minimize potential carbon emissions.

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References

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